

Prospects for Using Positive Chinese Experience of Physical Education in Educational Institutions

Zhenghua TANG ¹

Опубліковано	Секція	УДК
20.01.2025	Освіта/Педагогіка	796.011.1:378(510)

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14707976>

Annotation. The article emphasizes that it is in China that physical culture has acquired the status of one of the scientific directions of the education system and health improvement of the nation. The process of physical education in Chinese schools is aimed at educating the idea of "lifelong" physical exercises and sports, as well as developing a system of knowledge about physical fitness, motor skills, and habits of active motor activity. China has a long tradition of developing a system of physical education and sports, which causes high demographics in this country. This determines the expediency of studying and considering positive practices and experience in training physical education and sports specialists in Chinese universities, which is valuable in modernizing such specialists' national professional training system. The study substantiates the feasibility of implementing programs to promote physical activity among students in social networks, informing about preventive measures of general health care, promoting physical activity at the national level, allocating resources for preventive measures to promote physical activity, the structure of joint actions of stakeholders; development of national and international sports and fitness ties; monitoring recommended levels of physical activity for different population groups.

Keywords: physical culture, process of physical education, general pedagogical principles, China, training of specialists, education.

Перспективи використання позитивного китайського досвіду фізичного виховання та спорту в закладах освіти

Анотація. У статті наголошується, що фізична культура саме в Китаї набула статусу одного з наукових напрямів системи освіти і оздоровлення нації. Процес фізичного виховання в школах Китаю спрямований на виховання ідеї «довічних» занять фізичними вправами і спортом, розвиток системи знань про фізичну підготовку, рухові навички і звички активної рухової діяльності. Китай має давні традиції у розбудові системи фізичного виховання та спорту, що обумовлює високі демографічні показники в цій країні. Зазначене обумовлює доцільність вивчення та врахування позитивних практик і досвіду підготовки фахівців фізичного виховання та спорту в університетах Китаю, що є цінним в контексті модернізації національної системи професійної підготовки таких фахівців. Проведене дослідження обґрунтовує доцільність: упровадження програм популяризації фізичної активності студентської молоді в

¹ аспірант Сумського державного педагогічного університету імені А. С. Макаренка, ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-0754-1187>.

соціальних мережах; інформування про профілактичні заходи загальної охорони здоров'я; пропаганди фізичної активності на національному рівні; розподілу ресурсів на профілактичні заходи щодо пропаганди фізичної активності; структуру спільних дій стейкхолдерів; розвитку національних та міжнародних фізкультурно-спортивних зв'язків; моніторингу рекомендованих рівнів фізичної активності для різних груп населення.

Ключові слова: фізична культура, процес фізичного виховання, загально педагогічні принципи, Китай, підготовка фахівців, освіта.

Introduction

Problem statement. Among the countries of Asia, it is in China that physical culture has acquired the status of one of the scientific directions of the education system and health improvement of the nation. During the historical period of renewal in this country, high rates of socio-economic development, civic consciousness, and responsibility for the country's prestige have been achieved. China has become a highly developed industrial state with a high potential for developing science, education, culture, and sports (OECD Economic Surveys, 2015). The physical education process in Chinese schools aims to educate schoolchildren on "lifelong" physical exercises and sports, developing a system of knowledge about physical fitness, motor skills, and habits of active motor activity, including in extracurricular hours. In China, work is underway to introduce physical education as one of the subjects for entrance exams to certain universities. This experience is constantly generalized and improved for further dissemination.

Due to socially essential changes in the health care system and aspirations to enter the international space, Ukrainian educational institutions need to modify the content and organization of professional training specialists who will be competitive in the domestic and foreign labor markets.

China has a long tradition of building a system of physical education and sports, which causes high demographic indicators in this country. This determines the expediency of studying and considering positive practices and experience in training physical education and sports specialists in Chinese universities, which is valuable in modernizing such specialists' national system of professional training.

Analysis of current research. The analysis of scientific achievements testifies to the relevance at the national level of the problem of professional training of specialists in physical education and sports, which is confirmed by diverse scientific research on the professional development of specialists in physical education and sports in the conditions of higher education institutions (T. Boychuk, T. Bugeria, L. Sushchenko and others), on the health preservation of various specialists (O. Mikheenko and others), on the physical rehabilitation of persons of different nosologies and categories of the population (O. Hrytsyuk, O. Guzhalovsky, O. Marchenko, I. Mysula, V. Murza, V. Mukhin, S. Popov, etc.) etc.

The study of the works of foreign scientists on the aspects of professional training of future specialists in physical education and sports and comparative studies (Donnelly, Wiltshire, Hebert, Raffe, Brannen, Croxford, Martin, etc.) showed the expediency and importance of taking into account foreign experience for the dissemination of positive practices and innovative methods for training specialists. However, the peculiarities of professional training of future specialists in physical education and sports in educational institutions in China were not subjected to comparative analysis.

Our research is based on the most important regulations governing the training of bachelors of physical education in China [2; 4]: the Law of the People's Republic of China "On Compulsory Education" (1986), the Law of the People's Republic of China "On Education" (1995); Law of the People's Republic of China "On Higher Education" (1998), Regulations on Higher Education Institutions of the People's Republic of China (2021), Regulations on the

Organization and Conduct of the Educational Process in Higher Education Institutions of the People's Republic of China (2021), National Educational Program for Bachelors of Physical Education (2022), Qualification Requirements for Bachelors of Physical Education (2022), Methodological Recommendations for the Organization and Conduct of the Educational Process in Physical Education in colleges and universities (2021), and in Ukraine: the Law of Ukraine "On Education" (2017), the Law of Ukraine "On Higher Education" (2014), the Order of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine "Some Issues of Organizing Recruitment and Training", the Concept for the Development of Education in Ukraine for the Period up to 2015-2025. (2015), National Qualifications Framework (2011), Higher Education Standards for Educational Qualification Levels "Bachelor" and "Master" in the field of knowledge 01 "Education/Pedagogy" of specialty 016 "Physical Education" (2022), etc.

The article aims to highlight the prospects for using the positive Chinese experience of physical education and sports in educational institutions.

Results

Among the main goals of physical education are the promotion of general harmonious physical and mental development (intellectual, emotional, behavioral, social, as well as bodily and motor), the education of moral and volitional qualities, and the satisfaction of needs for movements and games. Sometimes, goals and objectives such as mastering the basics of popular sports, forming the ability to make independent decisions, promoting physical health and general emotional state, and improving the quality of life are formulated. Other significant tasks of physical education are the involvement of children and young people in sports activities, the acquisition of such motor skills as running, jumping, crawling, climbing, lifting and carrying loads, throwing, balance, protection, mastering fine motor skills, and thereby the development of abilities to act and adapt to the surrounding world, in which the processes of urbanization and industrialization are intensifying. Qualitatively organized physical education is more significant than ever in today's society; it guarantees the assimilation of behaviors such as safety actions, movement, swimming, etc. [8].

Various institutions and organizations in the field of physical culture and sports carry out specific functions related to the satisfaction of multiple needs of physical culture and sports orientation of people of different ages, interests, and material capabilities (primarily health, educational, publishing services); professional support of the production process of the industry is achieved by a multi-level system of personnel training provided by secondary and higher educational institutions, postgraduate education and various forms of advanced training; The management of the industry is carried out by the system of executive authorities of the state, regional and local levels, which develop a strategy for the development of physical culture and sports and are responsible for their implementation [3].

The main tasks in the national plan to develop sports and physical culture in China are popularizing sports and developing the Olympic spirit. We are talking about the need to use a variety of venues for both national and international competitions. The government undertakes to direct forces to the development of national sports organizations. Paragraph 8 of the development plan contains creating a unique global platform to exchange sports experiences among sports specialists, while the site should be open to everyone [1].

Let's look at the modern national plan for developing sports and physical culture in China, approved in July 2021 and designed for 5 years. The state's mission in the sports sector is to create a new concept for sports development, which will be aimed at implementing the strategy of a healthy China. China is interested in increasing the share of the population involved in sports. For this purpose, it seeks to build and improve sports infrastructure and hold national sports events on an ongoing basis. The plan describes in great detail the directions for attracting a more significant percentage of the population to sports, the need for accessibility of sports centers for the entire population, and increasing the motivation of all regions to raise the sports

level through participation in competitions and awarding winners [4]. It also mentions improving the education system, whose curriculum should include constant physical activity and sports activities.

Training physical education and sports specialists in ordinary colleges and universities that train physical education teachers is an integral part of China's higher teacher education. Over the years, China's brick-and-mortar colleges and universities have made significant strides in physical education. These specialties formed a particular scale of the system of training talents in physical education [4]. As of 2015, 248 regular colleges and universities in China major in physical education, including 16 sports colleges, 103 regular universities (colleges), and 129 comprehensive universities. The physical education specialties of these institutions have made a significant contribution to the national training of physical education talents for the development of sports science and technology and the promotion of physical education. Of course, since the expansion of enrollment in 1999, the enrollment for the specialty "physical education" has increased, and more and more students have the opportunity and hope to get higher education [4].

Specialties in physical education and sports, which can be obtained in these colleges and universities of the People's Republic of China, are a cradle for the education of physical education talents, and the training of talents is dynamic system engineering. Times change, society develops, and history moves forward, so the cultivation of talents must continue and improve. Teaching plays an important and active role in the talent learning process. Learning is a complex activity influenced by many factors and characterized by parametricity. The quality of teaching is the sum of multifactorial influences. Only by conducting an accurate and thorough analysis of the relationship between these factors and the quality of education is it possible to effectively control their action, strengthen teaching management, and improve its quality.

The educational process of physical education in the People's Republic of China (PRC) combines the teacher's activities and the students' training. Its quality is influenced not only by such micro factors as teachers, students, learning content, teaching tools, teaching methods, venue equipment, and teaching quality management methods but also by macro factors such as national economic conditions, policy orientation, and social environment. They directly or indirectly impact the quality of teaching in colleges and universities at different levels. With the continuous advancement of the process of popularizing higher education, people's attention has shifted from growth to improving quality, and ensuring the quality of teaching in physical education of bachelor's specialties has become one of the topical issues concerning people. Therefore, in the era of popularization of higher education, starting from the laws of the development of the specialty of physical education in ordinary colleges and universities to adaptation to the era of knowledge and information and the reform of basic education curricula, it is necessary to borrow the best practices in ensuring the quality of teaching in colleges and universities during the period of popularization of higher education in developed countries of the world.

To provide a guarantee of improving the quality of teaching, it is necessary (from the micro level to a deep understanding of the conditions of schooling, the status of students, the teaching staff, the mode of training talents, educational tasks and specifications, the curriculum, the equipment of the venue, the culture of the campus and other aspects of the process of training bachelor's specialists in physical education) find out the main factors affecting the quality of teaching physical education at this stage, by studying these main factors, as well as analyzing the main problems that need to be urgently solved, and on this basis, putting forward the main ideas for the development of quality assurance of teaching for bachelor's specialties in physical education, building a system for monitoring the quality of teaching, ensuring the quality of teaching and training. This is of great theoretical and practical importance for ensuring the quality of teaching physical education specialties in ordinary colleges and

universities at this stage and ensuring the sustainable development of physical education specialties [7].

In training specialists in physical education and sports in universities of the People's Republic of China, general pedagogical principles can be applied since this process is a remarkable phenomenon of training and upbringing [1].

The principle of awareness and activity is one of the basic principles of training bachelors in physical education. The success of any educational process depends on how consciously and actively students are involved in this work. A correct understanding of the tasks of the sports health process and their active implementation with interest speeds up the learning process and allows you to improve the acquired knowledge, skills, and abilities and creatively apply them in life. These laws primarily form the basis of the principle of consciousness and activity.

The principle of awareness and activity in the process of sports health is applied in the following: it develops an understanding of the common goal and specific tasks of the event and essential interests.

The principle of demonstration. In pedagogical practice, the demonstration should be understood as the performance of educational tasks by influencing students' visual, auditory, and cognitive senses. Demonstration plays a vital role in sports training since the activity is mainly practical and fulfills one of its special functions, for example, the comprehensive development of the senses. A direct demonstration in the sports training process is a demonstration of physical exercises and even a "feeling" of these exercises from personal experience. Direct demonstrations may include hands-on exercises and demonstrations. Indirect training includes, in particular, using pictures, diagrams, layouts, filmstrips, videos, and other visual aids, as well as various unique technical means.

The principle of execution and individualization is characterized by considering students' characteristics and how difficult or easy the task is. Sport means that the process of training and education should be organized, taking into account the capabilities of the participants, the level of training by age and gender, as well as individual differences in physical and mental abilities.

The principle of achievement is often expressed in terms from simple to complex. The process of individualizing classes or training exercises according to the age, gender, physical fitness, and capabilities of the participants requires unique tools and methods.

The principle of regularity is reflected in the regularity of sports and the alternation of rest with physical activity. The benefits of regular exercise are enormous. The regularity of the sports training process is characterized by the extent to which it depends mainly on the most convenient sequence of rest with exercises. Specialized classes will play an essential role in the process of playing sports. First, the necessary movements (especially arm movements) and skills are formed, and then basic skills such as leg and torso movements are improved.

The principle of development reflects the general orientation of the requirements for those engaged in sports training, the gradual increase in the volume and intensity of the associated tasks, and the setting and implementation of new and increasingly complex tasks.

Thus, the elements of the model for training future specialists in physical culture and sports in higher education institutions of the People's Republic of China include [6]:

- physical culture and pedagogical environment – includes the system of requirements of the PRC society for the training of specialists in physical culture and sports, implemented in regulatory acts;
- methodological environment – includes a system of methodological approaches and principles for training future specialists in physical culture and sports.
- material and technical environment – includes sports facilities, equipment, inventory, and other material resources that are necessary for physical exercises;
- social environment – includes people who participate in physical culture and sports, as well as social institutions that contribute to their development;

- methodological environment – includes methods, forms, and means of training future physical culture and sports specialists.

These elements are interrelated and influence each other. For example, modern sports facilities contribute to the development of physical culture and sports and increase interest among the population.

The main measures aimed at increasing the levels of physical activity in the PRC include [5]:

- comprehensive advertising that reflects the importance and benefits (economic, medical, biological, socio-psychological, etc., physical activity);
- rejection of normative sports and the distribution of sports shows, various entertainment sports festivals;
- encouraging physical activity in daily activities, carried out in cooperation with the relevant sectors;
- ensuring access for all people to forms of active mobility, in particular walking and cycling, and guaranteeing their safety;
- implementation of policies in the workplace that promote physical activity;
- creation of safe playgrounds and premises in schools where students could actively spend their free time;
- the formation of "quality physical education" to support the development of behavior patterns in children, thanks to which they will remain physically active throughout their lives;
- creation of sports and recreational facilities where everyone could play sports;
- improving the quality of physical education;
- versatile support for the commercial development of the physical culture and sports sectors, entrepreneurship in sports, and the provision of services;
- benefits for initiators, physically active and sports employees of the enterprise.

Social institutions such as schools, clubs, and sports organizations also play an essential role in developing physical culture and sports [2]. They provide access to exercise for different populations and educational and advocacy work. Physical conditions, such as climate and geographical location, can also affect the development of physical culture and sports. For example, in regions with a warm climate, people spend more time outdoors, which contributes to their physical development. The physical education environment is an essential factor affecting physical culture and sports development. Providing the right conditions for exercise is an important task for society.

Conclusions

The implementation of the PRC's experience in the development of high-quality physical education in colleges and universities of Ukraine is a complex concept that includes a reasonable structure of students' knowledge about sports and health, their possession of certain sports technologies and sports skills, the ability to conduct sports research, etc. However, it is not enough for students to master deep professional knowledge, certain sports techniques and skills, and scientific research and innovation opportunities. They still have to develop a serious attitude to work, a sense of cooperation and competition, high moral and psychological qualities, and social responsibility to adapt to society, serve society and meet social development needs.

The development and implementation of evidence-based national and regional guidelines on physical activity will make it possible to:

- to develop and implement information programs to increase the physical activity of student youth in the social networks;
- to inform about the national principles of physical activity and other preventive measures of general health;

- to determine the value-oriented starting point of physical culture and mass sports for the development of goals and objectives for the promotion of physical activity at the national level;
- to promote interdepartmental cooperation and the development of national goals and objectives for the promotion of physical activity;
- to identify the main reference points for the development of physical culture and mass sports for initiatives to promote physical activity;
- to justify the allocation of resources for preventive measures to promote physical activity;
- create a structure of joint actions for all stakeholders around one goal;
- to develop a science-based document that will allow all stakeholders to turn policies into actions with appropriate allocation of resources;
- to ensure national and international physical culture and sports relations with other regions and countries of the world in every possible way;
- promote the development of national mechanisms for surveillance and monitoring recommended physical activity levels for different populations.

References

1. Chen, Q., & Liu, T. (2020). The effectiveness of community sports provision on social inclusion and public health in rural China. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*, 17(2), 597. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17020597>.
2. Department of Sports Economy, General Administration of Sport of China. The data compilation of the sixth national sports venues census. URL: <http://www.sport.gov.cn/pucha/index.html>. Accessed Dec. 12, 2024.
3. Hallal, P.C., Andersen, L.B., Bull, F.C., Guthold, R., Haskell, W., & Ekelund, U. (2012). Global physical activity levels: surveillance progress, pitfalls, and prospects. *Lancet*, 380(9838), 247–257. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(12\)60646-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(12)60646-1).
4. Helen, M. (2016). China unveils The new National Fitness Plan. URL: <https://america.cgtn.com/2016/06/28/china-unveils-new-national-fitness-plan>. Accessed Oct. 11, 2024.
5. Liang, Z. (2023). Teaching quality management of physical education specialty in China and Ukraine. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education*. *IJERE*, 12(2), 1051-1058. <https://doi.org/10.11591/ijere.v12i2.24090>.
6. Ng, S.W., Norton, E.C., & Popkin, B.M. (2009). Why have physical activity levels declined among Chinese adults? Findings from the 1991–2006 China health and nutrition surveys. *Soc Sci Med.*, 68(7), 1305–1314. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2009.01.035>.
7. Zhang, X., Song, Y., Yang, T.B., Zhang, B., Dong, B., & Ma, J. (2012). Analysis of current situation of physical activity and influencing factors in Chinese primary and middle school students in 2010. *Zhonghua Yu Fang Yi Xue Za Zhi.*, 46(9), 781. <https://doi.org/10.3760/cma.j.issn.0253-9624.2012.09.003>.
8. Bakiko, I. (2010). Place of physical culture and sports in the leisure of youth. *Physical Education, Sports and Health Culture in Modern Society*, 3(11), 25-28.